

2-TOM, 5 - SON
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PHRASAL NOUN AND PHRASAL VERB

Yoqubova Charos Mansur qizi

2nd year student at the Jizzakh branch of the national university of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.

Supervisor: Teshaboyeva Nafisa

Abstract: This article explores the intricate difference between Phrasal verbs and phrasal nouns, and concept of both of them, their importance in English grammar. Many people know how to use them in grammar, but they aren't aware of difference of them. Phrasal noun and phrasal verb make our speech more expressive and efficient. They are common in daily talk. Instead of a long sentence, we use them to express ideas clearly and fast.

Key words: phrasal nouns and phrasal verbs, prepositions, combination of words, original phrasal verbs.

Introduction: Study of Phrasal noun and verb and their difference is main goal and important in this article. Throughout it, we can use them correctly and we will not confused them.

What is phrasal verb? It is a type verb that is formed by combining two or more verbs together to form a new verb. Example of original phrasal verb: back down. Verb example: You can't back down from a bully. Noun example: There was a backdown of tensions between the two sides.

While phrasal verbs are a series of two or three words together, like "Call back", phrasal nouns are usually one word, like "Call back" or two words connected with a hyphen, like "Flare-up".

2-TOM, 5 - SON

What is Phrasal noun? It is a consisting of a verb followed by a particle or preposition; the substantive counterpart of a phrasal verb, conveying gerundive meaning. “Break-in” is the phrasal noun from “break in”. They are formed by combining a verb and they help us say specific things in a shorter way.

Usually, we use phrasal verbs in the same way as regular verbs in a sentence. In addition, we often use them in spoken English and in an informal setting. Thus, it is best to avoid using these verbs in normal writing. Because phrasal verbs may have varied meanings, this might lead to an ambiguous context.

Examples: blow up, blow-up, blowup

- Blast off, blastoff
- Break away, breakaway
- Break out, breakout
- Carry on, carry-on
- Cash in, cash-in
- Die off, die-off

Phrasal verb is a verb consisting of two or more words—a verb and a preposition or a particle—that, when combined, describe an action. When formed into a closed or hyphenated compound, however, a phrasal verb is transformed into a phrasal noun, which can, alternatively, be employed as an adjective. Example: “start up” a company (phrasal verb) or work in a “start-up” (phrasal noun) - a small company. When a phrasal verb becomes a phrasal noun, sometimes the verb comes first, like “start-up” and sometimes the preposition comes first, such as “outbreak”.

Phrasal nouns frequently collocate with other words, forming natural combinations that are idiomatic and contribute to fluent language use.

Most phrasal verbs consist of a verb and adverb combined. Note that some of the adverbs involved can also function as prepositions, but don't let this confuse you. In the phrase “cool down the broth”, “down” is an adverb. Some do actually consist of a

2-TOM, 5 - SON

verb and a preposition, but these rarely cause problems. You aren't likely to write "would you look after my cat while I'm gone?"

Such nouns are often hyphenated, at least early in their history, but there is a strong tendency for such hyphenated form is usually the more formal one.

Phrasal verbs make up a huge category of expressions in English that careless users often misspell by substituting one-word noun forms for the standard two-word phrasal verb; for instance: it would have been a mistake for me to have written "Phrasal verbs makeup a huge category". It is fine to write "I didn't want to put on my make up" or "I had to take the makeup exam". (In this example "makeup "exam" is a noun acting like an adjective modifying another noun- "exam". What kind of exam was it? A makeup exam).

- Structure: Phrasal verb= verb +preposition or adverb
- Meaning: Different from the original verb
- Part of speech: Verb
- Example: "get up", "get in", "get over"
- Structure: Phrasal noun=noun +preposition or adverb
- Meaning: different from the original verb
- Part of speech: Noun
- Example:" a look", "a run", " a chat"

Phrasal verbs are verbs that are made up of a verb and a preposition or an adverb. They have a different meaning from the original verb.

Phrasal nouns are nouns that are made up of a verb and a preposition or an adverb. They have a different meaning from the original verb.

Conclusion:

In conclusion: the study of phrasal noun and phrasal verb in English linguistic offers valuable points. There are many examples of phrasal verbs and phrasal nouns in the article. And learners can take needed information from it. For instance: the

2-TOM, 5 - SON

preposition receives the word stress, but, when phrasal verbs are used in their compound noun form, the verb part of the phrase (the first part) receives the stress and etc.

References:

1. Banerjee, A and Watson, T.F.(2011) Pickard's manual of operative dentistry 9th ed. Oxford: Univer
2. Bauer Laurie, Huddleston Rodney and Pullum Geoffrey, 2002, "Lexical word-formation", The Cambridge Grammar of the English Language, Chapter19, 1621-1722.
3. Lakoff George & Johnson Mark. Metaphors we live by. - USA. The University of Chicago Press. 1980.
4. Mednicova E.M. Seminars in English Lexicology. Moscow, 1978.
5. Nida E.A. Morphology. The Descriptive Analysis of Words; University of Michigan, 1946.
6. Teshaboyeva, N, & Mamayoqubova, S.(2020). Communicative Approach to language teaching.
7. Teshaboyeva, N. (2020). Linguistic Personality, ITS STRUCTURAL CHARASTERICS IN THE NEW PERSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS.
8. Teshaboyeva , N Z,(2019). TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH LITERATURE INTESL AND TEFL CLASSROOMS.
9. Teshaboyeva, N, & Rayimberdiyev, S.(2023, May). The IMPORTANCE OF USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH CLASSES. In academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol.8, pp. 149-153)

2-TOM, 5 - SON

10.Nafisa, T, & Marina, S. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH VOCABULARY IN TEST AND TEFL CLASSROOMS. International Journal of contemporary Scientific and Technical research, 465-469.

